

Influence of Solvent on Reaction Rate and Mechanism

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A general equation for the variation of specific rate constant k with dielectric constant D for any reaction, in which the transition state may or may not be polarized and the slope of $\log k - D$ variation at any temperature may be positive or negative, has been proposed. This equation was proved to be applicable to usual reactions as well as those exhibiting minima or maxima with solvent composition variation. The best method for computation of a_{\pm} , the distance of closest approach of solvent molecules to the transition state in a bimolecular reaction, has been developed. The acid hydrolysis of propionamide has been studied, in dioxane water solvent mixtures at five temperatures within the range 25-65°, in the light of the proposed relations. The influence of the solvent on the reaction mechanism, which explains the kinetic data, has been quantitatively studied and discussed.

RECENTLY, a method for calculating b^* , the distance of closest approach of solvent molecules to the activated complex in a bimolecular reaction has been suggested¹. Following the method of Laidler and Landskroener², the relationship of k , the rate constant to both D , the dielectric constant and T , the absolute temperature for an ion-dipole type of bimolecular reaction has been expressed¹ in the general form,

$$\log k = \log k_0 + \frac{X}{TD} + \frac{Y}{T}, \quad \dots (1)$$

where X and Y are numbers depending on the distribution of charges, the dielectric constant of solute and b^* . According to the authors treatment¹, the X value could be obtained from the slope of the linear plots of $\log k$ against $1/D$ and the mean value of Y between two temperatures close to the experimental temperature could be determined from the expression,

$$\log \frac{k_1}{k_2} = \left(\frac{X_1}{D_1 T_1} - \frac{X_2}{D_2 T_2} \right) + Y \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \quad \dots (2)$$

where the terms with subscripts 1 and 2 represent their values at temperatures T_1 and T_2 . Thus using the values of X and Y , the b^* values could be calculated. Those authors¹ studied the alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in DMSO-water mixtures [5-25% (v/v) of DMSO] in a very small range of dielectric constant variation ($D=76.43-75.80$ and $74.73-74.05$ at 30.2 and 35°, respectively). Using the size of OH^- ion (3.69 Å) in aqueous medium, the average value of b^* calculated was 2.415 Å. They¹ believe their method to be quite convincing. However, in their treatment we must point out that: X and Y given in equation (1) are functions of (dependent on) solvent composition,

and are not constants for different solvents at any given temperature as reported¹.

The aim of the present work is to 1) propose a more general equation for the variation of specific rate constant with dielectric constant for any reaction, 2) test the applicability of the proposed equation to usual reactions as well as reactions exhibiting minima or maxima with solvent composition variation, 3) develop the best method for computation of the distance of closest approach of solvent molecules to the transition state, and 4) discuss the role and influence of solvent on reaction mechanism.

Dioxane is completely miscible in all proportions with water. However, this property, combined with a very low dielectric constant, makes dioxane-water mixture highly suitable as solvents for the study of the reaction rates and mechanisms in media of continuously and rapidly varying dielectric constant. The acid hydrolysis of formamide⁵ and acetamide⁶ has been investigated in these solvents. The reaction rates were found to pass through minima with progressive addition of dioxane. In the present paper, the acid hydrolysis of propionamide in dioxane-water solvent mixtures was studied in order to apply the data thus obtained together with data in literature to verify the above mentioned aim.

Theoretical:

In recent theories of the solvent effect on reaction rates and mechanisms, the dielectric constant of the medium plays a very important role. The influence of dielectric constant on reaction velocity, at any tempera-

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ture, has been given by Elsemongy's equation⁴,

$$k = k' e^{\alpha(D-1)}, \quad \dots (3)$$

where k is the velocity constant, k' is its value at $D=1$, and α is a constant. This relation predicts a linear dependence of $\log k$ on D and it was reported⁴ to be valid in aqueous-organic mixed solvents over a wide range of dielectric constant. However, the plot of $\log k$ versus D for the acid hydrolysis of acetamide⁷ in isopropanol-water mixtures gave two linear portions of positive slopes separated by a sharp boundary at each temperature, and it is reported⁷ that Elsemongy's equation⁴ is obeyed for each linear part in the alcohol- and water-rich regions. Moreover, in reactions exhibiting minima^{5,6}, the plot of $\log k$ versus D gave two linear portions of positive and negative slopes in the water and dioxane-rich mixtures respectively. So, at any temperature, there are two values for k' corresponding to the two linear portions in the two regions⁵.

It is necessary now to propose a more general equation for the variation of specific rate constant with dielectric constant of the medium for any reaction. It has been found that the change with temperature of the dielectric constant of the pure solvents and the solvent-water mixtures may be expressed^{8,9} with considerable accuracy by equation (4).

$$\log D = \log a - b T, \text{ or, } \log \frac{a}{D} = b T \quad \dots (4)$$

where a and b are empirical constants^{8,9}. Equation (4) has also been tested⁸ using a number of series of data in the literature. The results indicate that equation (4) is valid⁸ within the experimental errors over a temperature range of at least 150°.

Substitution of the T value from equation (4) in Arrhenius equation,

$$\log k = \log A - \frac{E}{2.3026 R} \frac{1}{T} \quad \dots (5)$$

yields,

$$\log k = \log A - \frac{E b}{2.3026 R} \frac{1}{\log(a/D)} \quad \dots (6)$$

Equation (6), is a general equation, represents the variation of specific rate constant at various temperatures with the corresponding dielectric constant of the medium for any solvent composition. The plot of $\log k$ against $1/\log(a/D)$ should yield a straight line of a negative slope ($-Eb/2.3026 R$) and an intercept $\log A$, for each solvent composition.

The value of k' may be obtained from equation (6) by putting $D=1$, thus,

$$\log k' = \log A - \frac{E b}{2.3026 R} \frac{1}{\log a} \quad \dots (7)$$

The value of k' varies with solvent composition and in each, it corresponds certain temperature at which $D=1$. Generally, the dielectric constant decreases, as the temperature rises^{8,9}, and reaches unity at high temperatures. If equation (4) is assumed to hold in the temperature range 0-1000°, the calculated temperatures corresponding to $D=1$ are shown in Table 3. Thus, the calculated k' values, from equation (7), are practically reasonable and possible at the temperatures indicated.

The relationship between k and k' can be obtained, from equations (6) and (7), by eliminating $\log A$.

$$\log k = \log k' - \frac{E b}{2.3026 R} \left(\frac{1}{\log(a/D)} - \frac{1}{\log a} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

This equation predicts that, at different temperatures, $\log k$ will vary linearly with $1/\log(a/D)$ for any solvent composition, and thus the k' value can be calculated from the intercept to a good accuracy without any doubt. Equation (8) is a more general rate equation which predicts the effect of the solvent (dielectric constant) on any type of reactions, in which the transition state may or may not be polarized and the slope of $\log k$ - D variation at any temperature may be positive or negative.

Experimental

The purification of propionamide and dioxane was described^{2,3} before. The preparation of solutions, kinetic procedure and the experimental details have been reported elsewhere⁵. All compositions were accurate to within ± 0.02 wt %. All solutions were freshly prepared before taking measurements. The dielectric constants of dioxane-water solvent mixtures were obtained by calculation and interpolation from the data of Åkerlof⁸.

Results and Discussion

The acid hydrolysis of propionamide has been studied in water and in dioxane-water mixtures (upto 80% by weight dioxane) at five temperatures within the range 25-65°. The rate constants are listed in Table 1 for various temperatures and solvent compositions. Each is the mean of at least, and generally of more than, two experiments. The values of k , the second order velocity constant are those found from the best straight line drawn through the experimental points. Rate constants were generally reproducible to within $\pm 1\%$. Plots of $\log k$ against $1/T$ for the reaction in the different solvent mixtures gave practically good straight lines showing that the data follow Arrhenius equation very closely. The values of the activation energy, E , and frequency factor, $\log A$, were evaluated from the least square slopes and intercepts of these lines, and are collected in Table 1.

The specific reaction rate (in liter mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹) of the acid hydrolysis of propionamide in dioxane-water

TABLE 1—VELOCITY CONSTANTS (IN LITER MOLE⁻¹ SEC⁻¹), ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION (IN JOULE MOLE⁻¹) AND FREQUENCY FACTORS IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Dioxane Wt %	10 ⁵ k					E ± 495	log A ± 0.08
	25°C	35°C	45°C	55°C	65°C		
0	1.0715	3.2050	8.6144	21.630	52.834	81410	9.30
5	1.0463	3.1053	8.3556	20.908	50.919	81169	9.25
10	1.0225	3.0103	8.0917	20.200	48.994	80880	9.18
20	0.9737	2.8125	7.5694	18.758	45.137	80270	9.06
30	0.9257	2.6181	7.0506	17.352	41.370	79600	8.91
40	0.8772	2.4200	6.5222	15.889	37.478	78763	8.74
50	0.8278	2.2239	5.9931	14.444	33.669	77843	8.55
60	0.9111	2.5219	6.9556	17.389	41.434	80214	9.01
65	0.9951	2.8403	7.9444	20.222	49.134	81865	9.34
70	1.0787	3.1561	8.9167	23.000	56.741	83125	9.6
75	1.1644	3.4792	9.9028	25.856	64.581	84179	9.8
80	1.2486	3.7988	10.8861	28.667	72.391	85054	10.0

mixtures can be represented as a function of temperature T (in °K) by equation (9).

$$\ln k = a' - b'T \quad \dots (9)$$

The values of the constants a' and b' were evaluated by the method of least squares and are compiled in Table 2, for each solvent composition. The velocity constants calculated from equation (9) at the five temperatures are accurate within the experimental error for the various dioxane-water solvents.

The addition of dioxane to water first causes a decrease of reaction rate, activation energy or frequency factor, to a minimum at about 54% by weight dioxane, which is then followed by an increase on further dioxane addition. However, the effect of solvent on reaction rate is more pronounced on increasing the temperature. This behaviour for the specific reaction rate was recently reported for acetamide⁵ and formamide⁶ hydrolyses in dioxane-water solvent mixtures. Accordingly, it is possible to correlate the reaction rate with solvent effects in the same manner^{5,6}. The decrease in activation energy may be due to more solvation of the activated complex than of the reactants.

Solvation effects and activation parameters :

The influence of solvent variation on reaction rate may be examined in terms of changes in the activation parameters. These parameters are usually taken as a measure of the solvation effects, and can be calculated by applying the usual thermodynamic relations to the temperature variation of the rate constant in various dioxane-water solvents. According to the theory of absolute reaction rates the rate constant is related to the free energy of activation, ΔG*, by the equation

$$k = \frac{K T}{h} e^{-\Delta G^*/RT}$$

Thus, ΔG* can be represented as a function of temperature by (10).

$$\Delta G^* = RT \left(\ln \frac{KT}{h} - \ln k \right) = R(T \ln T + c T + b') \dots (10)$$

where $c = \ln \frac{K}{h} - a'$. The value of the constant c for each solvent composition was evaluated, and is given in Table 2. Thus,

$$\Delta S^* = -d(\Delta G^*)/dT = -R(\ln T + 1 + c) \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\Delta H^* = \Delta G^* + T \Delta S^* = R(b' - T) \quad \dots (12)$$

TABLE 2—CONSTANTS OF EQUATIONS (9-12) FOR EVALUATION OF K AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND THERMODYNAMIC ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AT 25°C, IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Dioxane Wt %	a'	b'	c	25°C		
				ΔG* ± 952 J mole ⁻¹	ΔH* - ΔS* ± 495 J mole ⁻¹	± 1.5 K ⁻¹
0	21.4130	9792.42	2.3469	101360	78939	75.2
5	21.2903	9763.41	2.4696	101423	78698	76.2
10	21.1487	9728.56	2.6112	101484	78408	77.4
20	20.8500	9655.27	2.9100	101615	77799	79.9
30	20.5245	9574.66	3.2355	101752	77129	82.6
40	20.1279	9473.97	3.6321	101898	76291	85.9
50	19.6934	9363.30	4.0665	102055	75371	89.5
60	20.7444	9648.52	3.0155	101821	77743	80.8
65	21.5022	9847.13	2.2578	101594	79394	74.5
70	22.0941	9998.61	1.6658	101386	80654	69.5
75	22.5987	10125.47	1.1612	101190	81708	65.3
80	23.0240	10230.66	0.7360	101010	82583	61.8

The calculated thermodynamic parameters of activation at 25° for various solvent compositions are recorded in Table 2 and are shown in Fig. 1. It is seen that ΔG* increases gradually and linearly with successive dioxane addition up to about 54% by weight and then decreases, also linearly, by further progressive addition of the organic solvent. According to the theory of absolute reaction rates, the increase of ΔG* is a sign of solvation of the reacting species.

Some useful insight with regard to the changes in the structural aspects of the solvents might be obtained from the changes in enthalpy and entropy, which contain important structural contributions⁸. The enthalpy change decreases gradually with increasing dioxane content up to about 54% by weight, and thereafter increases with progressive addition of dioxane.

It has been pointed out¹⁰ that the stabilisation of the activated complex by the solvent involves restriction of motion of some of the solvent molecules. Solvents

Fig. 1. Variation of activation parameters with solvent composition at 25°

having permanent dipole moments will, therefore, be preferentially oriented such that an attractive interaction rather than repulsion takes place. On the other hand, non-polar solvents will be relatively unoriented and hence will have higher entropy of activation. These solvents will, therefore, have a greater loss in entropy as a result of solvation, and reactions in these solvents will consequently have a large negative entropy of activation.

However, ΔS^* , which has large negative values, decreases with increasing dioxane content up to about 54% by weight, and thereafter increases with further dioxane addition.

The sudden variation of thermodynamic parameters of activation noticed at around 54% by weight of dioxane reflects the variation of reaction kinetics with solvent composition. As mentioned above, minimum rate constant was observed at about 54% by weight of dioxane.

Influence of dielectric constant on reaction rate :

To test equation (6) in a more precise manner, it may be put in the form

$$\log \frac{A}{k} = \frac{E b}{2.3026 R} \frac{1}{\log (a/D)}, \text{ or, } \dots (13)$$

$$\log \frac{A}{k} \log \frac{a}{D} = \frac{E b}{2.3026 R} = \text{constant.}$$

For any solvent composition, a plot of $\log (A/k)$ vs $1/\log (a/D)$ values at different temperatures should yield a straight line, passing through the origin, and of positive slope ($Eb/2.3026 R$). From the Arrhenius calculated E values, the b values may be calculated for each solvent composition and compared with the reported⁸ b values. Applicability of the developed relation to sixty sets of recently published data on the effects of solvents on the acid and base hydrolyses of amides, anilides and esters (including usual reactions as well as those exhibiting minima or maxima with solvent composition variation) has been examined. Practically, this is the case and the agreement was generally very well. Åkerlöf⁹ reported that the constant b is a very important factor in the theory for heats of dilution.

Also, from equation (13), a plot of $\log (A/k)$ vs $Eb/\log (a/D)$ should yield a straight line passing through the origin for all data in different solvent compositions at different temperatures since the slope is always $1/2.3026 R$. With more than 600 experimental points, a practically good straight line passing through the origin was obtained and the value of R calculated was $8.3144 \text{ J mole}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. We must, therefore, expect that any reaction obeying Arrhenius equation should follow equations (6), (8) and (13).

The acid hydrolysis of propionamide has been studied in dioxane-water solvents in different dielectric media in the range 7.85-8.7. Starting from the point of minimum reaction rate (at around 54 wt % dioxane), the rate increases either on increasing (water-rich region) or decreasing (dioxane-rich region) the dielectric constant. At any temperature, $\log k$ was found to be linearly dependent on D and gave curves with $1/D$, in both regions.

The influence of dielectric constant on reaction rate, for any solvent composition, may now be best investigated on the basis of our new proposed equations. Equation (13), for example, predicts a linear dependence of $\log (A/k)$ on $1/\log (a/D)$ for any solvent composition. Practically good straight lines passing through the origin were generally obtained, and typical plots in the water-rich region (0-50 wt % dioxane) are shown in Fig. 2, for propionamide hydrolysis in dioxane-water solvents. The least square calculated values of $\log k'$ are given in Table 3.

Elsemongy⁴ deduced equations which relate to the rate constant of a reaction to the dielectric constant of the solution, its ionic strength and temperature. These are applicable to ion-ion, ion-dipole and dipole-dipole reactions. Values of distances of closest approach, a_{\pm} for the activated complex were estimated by substitution in equations⁴ for the different values of $\ln k$, $\ln k'$ and D at different temperatures. At any tempera-

Fig. 2. Influence of dielectric constant on rate constant

TABLE 3—CONSTANTS FOR EVALUATION OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS, CALCULATED T°K AT UNIT DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND LOG K' VALUES FOR VARIOUS SOLVENT COMPOSITIONS

Dioxane Wt %	C _S mo/e/l	C _{H₂O} mole/l	log a*	b	T°K at which D = 1	log k'
0	0.000	55.51	2.50606	0.00205	1222.5	5.8207
5	0.568	52.73	2.49248 ^ψ	0.00209 ^ψ	1192.6	5.6906
10	1.135	49.96	2.48417	0.00215	1155.5	5.5283
20	2.270	44.41	2.45166	0.00224	1094.5	5.2241
30	3.405	38.86	2.40984	0.00233	1034.3	4.8936
40	4.540	33.31	2.35179	0.00241	975.8	4.5262
50	5.675	27.75	2.27118	0.00247	919.5	4.1326
60	6.810	22.20	2.15484	0.00249	865.4	4.1663
65	7.378	19.43	2.07052 ^ψ	0.00247 ^ψ	838.3	4.2391
70	7.945	16.65	1.97822	0.00245	807.4	4.2151
75	8.513	13.88	1.86669 ^ψ	0.00240 ^ψ	777.8	4.1660
80	9.080	11.10	1.70059	0.00225	755.8	4.1275

* Calculated on the absolute temperature scale

ψ Calculated from the interpolated values

it was supposed²⁻⁷ that the catalysing ion is unipolar in character ($Z_A = 1$) whereas the amide molecule is a dipole. The dipole moment and radius of the propionamide molecule were taken¹¹ as equal to 3.85×10^{-18} esu and 3.07×10^{-8} cm, respectively. The radius of the hydronium ion²⁻⁴ was taken as 1.7×10^{-8} cm. The results of our calculations at 25, 45 and 65°, are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DISTANCES OF CLOSEST APPROACH, a_{\pm} , FOR THE ACTIVATED COMPLEX AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Dioxane Wt %	D					a_{\pm}		
	25°C	35°C	45°C	55°C	65°C	25°C	45°C	65°C
0	78.5	74.9	71.4	68.1	65.0	3.119	3.137	3.154
5	74.0	70.5	67.2	64.1	61.1	3.136	3.155	3.173
10	69.7	66.3	63.1	60.1	57.2	3.158	3.178	3.198
20	60.8	57.7	54.8	52.1	49.5	3.199	3.221	3.243
30	51.9	49.2	46.6	44.2	41.9	3.243	3.268	3.293
40	43.0	40.7	38.5	36.4	34.4	3.293	3.321	3.349
50	34.3	32.4	30.6	28.9	27.3	3.346	3.377	3.407
60	25.8	24.4	23.0	21.8	20.6	3.337	3.370	3.405
65	21.6	20.4	19.3	18.2	17.2	—	—	—
70	17.7	16.7	15.8	14.9	14.1	3.320	3.357	3.394
75	14.2	13.4	12.7	12.0	11.4	—	—	—
80	10.7	10.2	9.7	9.2	8.7	3.296	3.335	3.373

Fig. 3. Dependence of distance of closest approach for the activated complex on solvent composition

ture a_{\pm} varies with solvent composition, i.e., with dielectric constant⁴. In the acid hydrolysis of amides,

At any temperature, the a_{\pm} value increases on successive addition of dioxane, reaches a maximum at around 54% by weight (minimum reaction rate) and thereafter decreases on further dioxane addition (Fig. 3). As the distance of closest approach for the activated complex decreases, the reacting species become closer to each other, and the reaction rate increases. This may explain the variation of reaction rate with solvent composition and may also account for the solvation of the activated complex. According to the Kirkwood theory^{1,2} these radii should not correspond to the over-all radii but should be effective radii related to the size of the active groups in the complex molecules. Therefore the essential factor is the closeness of approach of the solvent molecules to the seat of reaction. The distance of C-O bond reported¹ is of the order 1.43 Å. Therefore it is reasonable that the new bond which is being formed in the transition state due to the attack of H_3O^+ ion (its radius was taken²⁻⁴ as 1.7 Å) on the carbonyl oxygen atom of the amide is of the order $1.43 + 1.7 = 3.13$ Å. This value is in full agreement with our calculated value of 3.119 Å at 25° in the aqueous medium. On this basis the values calculated are entirely reasonable and give an idea about the extent of solvation.

Thus, the best method for computation of the distance of closest approach of solvent molecules to the transition state is to (1) calculate the value of $\log k'$ using one of our proposed equations (7) or (8), and (2) substitute in equations⁴ for the different values of $\ln k$, $\ln k'$ and D at different temperatures.

However, a weakness in Elsemongy's calculations⁴ is the assumption of constant radii for reactant particles at all temperatures and all solvent compositions when calculating theoretical activated complex radii from the derived equations⁴. In addition, constant radii for reactant particles were assumed even when the nature of the second component of the solvent changed completely⁴. It would be seen that not only the radius of the intermediate complex, but also the radii of reactant particles should all change with the nature of solvent, with the composition of a given solvent pair, and with the temperature for a given solvent. However, further investigations^{1,2} would be helpful to account for these defects and to throw more light on the influence of solvent on reaction rates and mechanisms.

Proposed mechanism :

A bimolecular mechanism for the acid hydrolysis of acetamide in aqueous-organic mixed solvents was recently reported⁵. Based on the experimental findings, this mechanism was modified in a more general form to account for the influence of the solvent on the acid hydrolysis of propionamide. Our proposed protolytic mechanism may be simply represented as follows :

where A is the amide molecule, S is an organic solvent molecule and T^+ stands for the solvated transition state in which the solvation is maintained through H-bonding. One must also consider the equilibrium³ $H_3O^+ + S \rightleftharpoons SH^+ + H_2O$. For this reaction, the equilibrium constant will be written as

$$K = C_{SH^+} + C_{H_2O} / C_{H_3O^+} + C_S \quad \dots (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } (C_{H_3O^+})_{total} &= C_{H_3O^+} + C_{SH^+} \\ &= (C_{SH^+} C_{H_2O} / K C_S) + C_{SH^+} \\ &= C_{SH^+} (1 + C_{H_2O} / K C_S) \quad \dots (16) \end{aligned}$$

Application of the steady-state treatment of the species T^+ and substituting in the rate expression, one gets,

$$\text{the rate} = k_2 C_T^+ C_{H_2O} = \frac{k_1 k_2 C_A C_{SH^+}}{k_{-1} C_S / C_{H_2O} + k_2} \quad \dots (17)$$

Substitution of the value of C_{SH^+} from equation (16) into equation (17), we obtain

$$\text{the rate} = \frac{k_1 k_2 C_A}{k_{-1} C_S / C_{H_2O} + k_2} \frac{(C_{H_3O^+})_{total}}{1 + C_{H_2O} / K C_S}$$

The observed second-order rate constant is therefore given by

$$k = \frac{k_1 k_2}{(k_{-1} C_S / C_{H_2O} + k_2) (1 + C_{H_2O} / K C_S)} \quad \dots (18)$$

Equation (18), on arrangement, gives

$$\frac{1}{k} = \left(\frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2} \frac{C_S}{C_{H_2O}} \right) + \left(\frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2 K} + \frac{1}{k_1 K} \frac{C_{H_2O}}{C_S} \right) \quad (19)$$

The minimum of a reaction rate indicates a compensation of two opposing factors affecting the reaction rate. It is obvious, from equation (19), that k is dependent on both C_{H_2O} / C_S and C_S / C_{H_2O} . So, this may explain the variation of rate constant with solvent composition. If the reactions were catalysed only by SH^+ ion, the second-order velocity constant would be given, from equation (17) as

$$k_{SH^+} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1} C_S / C_{H_2O} + k_2} \quad \dots (20)$$

which, on rearrangement, gives

$$\frac{1}{k_{SH^+}} = \frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2} \frac{C_S}{C_{H_2O}} \quad \dots (21)$$

On the other hand, substitution of C_{SH^+} into equation (17) by its value from equation (15) gives the velocity constant of the reaction if it were catalysed only by H_3O^+ ion.

$$k_{H_3O^+} = \frac{k_1 k_2 K}{k_{-1} + k_2 C_{H_2O}/C_S} \quad \dots (22)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{H_3O^+}} = \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2 K} + \frac{1}{k_1 K} \frac{C_{H_2O}}{C_S} \quad \dots (23)$$

Comparison of equations (21) and (23) with equation (19) leads to equations (24) and (25).

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{k_{SH^+}} + \frac{1}{k_{H_3O^+}} \quad \dots (24)$$

$$k = \frac{k_{SH^+} k_{H_3O^+}}{k_{SH^+} + k_{H_3O^+}} \quad \dots (25)$$

It is clear, from equations (24) and (25), that if $k_{H_3O^+}$ is much smaller than k_{SH^+} the observed second-order rate constant k will be nearly given by $k_{H_3O^+}$. From equations (20) and (22), we obtain

$$k_{H_3O^+}/k_{SH^+} = K C_S/C_{H_2O} = C_{SH^+}/C_{H_3O^+} \quad \dots (26)$$

and thus, from equations (24) and (26),

$$k_{H_3O^+}/k = 1 + K C_S/C_{H_2O} \text{ and } k_{SH^+}/k = 1 + C_{H_2O}/K C_S \quad \dots (27)$$

So, if the value of the equilibrium constant K (equation 15) is known in dioxane-water mixtures, the values of both $k_{H_3O^+}$ and k_{SH^+} may be calculated for any solvent composition.

Now it is obvious, from equation (19), that in the water-rich regions the contribution of the first term in the bracket to the observed rate constant predominates, whereas the contribution of the second term predominates in the dioxane-rich region. Thus, to test the validity of our proposed equations, $1/k$ was plotted versus C_S/C_{H_2O} and versus C_{H_2O}/C_S in the water-rich (0-50 wt % dioxane) and in the dioxane-rich (60-80 wt % dioxane) regions, respectively. From the initial rate slope and intercept in each region, the k_{-1}/k_2 ratio

can be determined and compared to each other. In the former case, from the initial slope of the curve obtained $\left(\frac{1}{k_1} \frac{k_{-1}}{k_2}\right)$ and its initial intercept $\left(\frac{1}{k_1}\right)$, the k_{-1}/k_2 ratio equals 2.25 at 25°. In the latter case, practically linear plot was obtained at the same temperature; from its slope $\left(\frac{1}{k_1 K}\right)$ and intercept $\left(\frac{k_{-1}}{k_2} \frac{1}{k_1 K}\right)$, the k_{-1}/k_2 ratio was found to be 4.27. Thus, the k_{-1}/k_2 ratio varies from 2.25 to 4.7 on passing from water-rich to dioxane-rich regions. The linear dependence of $1/k$ on C_{H_2O}/C_S in the dioxane-rich region shows that the contribution of the first term in equation (19) is mainly negligible, and that the k_{-1}/k_2 ratio (or k_2) is almost constant in this region.

The values of the Arrhenius parameters for the acid hydrolysis of propionamide in dioxane-water solvents together with the thermodynamic activation parameters are all consistent with the above considerations and confirm our proposed mechanism for the reaction.

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References

1. LALLAN SINGH, R. T. SINGH R. K. SINGH and R. C. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 372.
2. K. J. LAIDLER and P. A. LANDSKROENER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 200.
3. E. S. AMIS and J. F. HINTON, *Solvent Effects on Chemical Phenomena*, Vol. I. Academic Press, New York, London, 1973.
4. M. M. ELSEMONGY, *Z. Physik Chem. Neue Folge*, 1973, 84, 294.
5. M. M. ELSEMONGY, M. S. ABU ELAMAYEM and M. MOUSSA, *Z. Physik. Chem. Neue Folge*, 1975, 95, 215.
6. M. M. ELSEMONGY and H. M. ABU ELNADER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 1055.
7. M. M. ELSEMONGY, M. S. ABU ELAMAYEM, M. MOUSSA and M. GOUDA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1130.
8. G. ÅKERLOF and O. A. SHORT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1241.
9. G. ÅKERLOF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4125.
10. K. B. WIBERG, *Physical Organic Chemistry*, John Wiley, New York, 1963.
11. M. E. HOBBS and W. W. BATES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 746.
12. To be published.